

1 **An HT-29 model of *Campylobacter concisus* infection.**

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8 In an HT-29 model of *Campylobacter concisus* infection, the gene most perturbed transcriptome-wide as
9 was the cystic fibrosis transmembrane receptor, *CFTR*. Transcriptomics powered by RNA-sequencing has
10 the capacity to illustrate difficult to discern molecular dynamics in disease biology.

11 Citations

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